

Codebook

Aikido Interaction Training Experiment

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1 Aikido Model (+)

Principles of the aikido interaction model: 11 principles in 3 clusters.

1.1 Curiosity

To have the motivation to interact, discover and learn > tranquillity cluster.

1.2 Unification

To blend with the other person by fostering physical closeness, sensitivity and a willingness to build common ground > connection cluster.

1.3 Tough

Attunement with accelerating speed and power > connection cluster.

1.4 Safety

Respect for the integrity of the environment, other and self > ecology cluster.

1.5 Balance soft and tough

Sensitivity to balance toughness and softness > connection cluster.

1.6 ECOLOGY

Ecology cluster: safety, context, and noble outcomes.

1.7 Context

An awareness of space, time, bodies and beings > ecology cluster.

1.8 Openness

An inviting, positive, non-judgmental attitude > tranquillity cluster.

1.9 Soft

Attunement with decelerating speed and power > connection cluster.

1.10 Circulation

Dynamic synergy promoting reciprocal influence > connection cluster.

1.11 Other-relative view

Taking the perspective of the other > connection cluster.

1.12 Noble outcome

Appropriate results for any party involved > ecology cluster.

1.13 CONNECTION

Connection cluster: circulation, unification, other-relative view, toughness, and softness.

1.14 TRANQUILLITY

Calmness, centredness, groundedness and alertness > tranquillity cluster (+ curiosity + openness).

2 Pedagogical processes

Pedagogical processes that characterise the training days in the experiment.

2.1 Clarity

Structure, content, form, instructions, navigation, non-alienating, and positive

2.2 Effort

Effortful learning, stretching without overdoing.

2.3 Multiple coding

Multiples communication channels:

- Dual coding - comparison group - visual and verbal.
- Triple coding - embodiment group - bodily, visual, and verbal.

2.4 Relevance

Relatable and actionable: needs, content, and cases.

2.5 Safety

Trust, authority, liking, and social proof for physical, psychological, and cultural safety.

2.6 Spacing

Spreading, varying, retrieving, and interleaving.

3 Memory performance

Learning gain: retention, assimilation, and application.

3.1 Response effect

Mentioning questionnaire response effect: the act of administering a questionnaire or survey itself influences participants' responses. For instance, it reminds participants of the training day and their code sentences.

3.2 Embodied memory

Applying what is learned in an aikido-embodied class requires that the teacher guides the bodily movements and its transfer to a meaningful message. It also requires that learners retain the knowledge and skills in memory and use them effectively. It is believed that the integration of movement and physical activity leads to better cognitive and learning outcomes (Mavilidi et al., 2022, p. 15).

3.3 Social touch

Biological, neuroscience, and biobehavioral research has described how touch and bodily interactions create attunement, synchrony, empathic resonance, and linkage (Behrens et al., 2020; Denk et al., 2020; Mayo et al., 2021; Palumbo et al., 2017). The researchers conclude that social touch promotes physiological co-regulation and positively impacts social engagement and emotional regulation.

3.4 Somatic learning

Particular posture, movement, and breathing techniques mediate tranquility and change the learner's mental and physiological processes (Hanna, 1986; Mavilidi et al., 2022; Oswald et al., 2023; Swinnen, 2023). These changes promote self-regulation and can be measured with biofeedback instruments (Naves-Bittencourt et al., 2015).

3.5 Retention

The training remains in the memory for a long time and the participant easily applies the insights and skills from the training.

3.6 Actionability

Putting learning into action after the training day.

4 Course satisfaction

4.1 Dissatisfied aikido-embodied :-)

Expressing dissatisfaction with aikido-embodied training.

4.2 Dissatisfied comparison :-)

Expressing dissatisfaction with comparison training.

4.3 Satisfied aikido-embodied :-)

Expressing satisfaction and/or gratefulness with aikido-embodied training.

4.4 Satisfied comparison :-)

Expressing satisfaction and/or gratefulness with comparison training.

4.5 Content satisfaction

Satisfaction with the training content.

4.5.1 Exceeded content

Exceeded content expectations.

4.5.2 Satisfied content

Satisfied with the training content.

4.5.3 Not satisfied content

Not satisfied with the training content..

4.6 Method satisfaction

Satisfaction with the training method.

4.6.1 Exceeded method

Exceeded method expectations.

4.6.2 Satisfied method

Satisfied with the training method.

4.6.3 Not satisfied method

Not satisfied with the training method.

4.7 Trainer didactics satisfaction

Satisfaction with the way the teacher taught.

4.7.1 Exceeded trainer didactics

Exceeded trainer didactics expectations.

4.7.2 Satisfied trainer didactics

Satisfied with the trainer didactics.

4.7.3 Not satisfied trainer didactics

Not satisfied with the trainer didactics.

5 Course parameters

Elements of the training course the participants referred to.

5.1 THEORY

The theory concepts.

5.1.1 Scientific

The concepts and interaction model based on research.

5.2 REFLECTION

The self-reflection moments to adopt the theory concepts.

5.3 ACTIVATION

The discussions in small groups to activate the theory concepts.

5.4 PLENARY FEEDBACK

Debriefing of the activation.

5.5 (Inter)active

Active participation (physical) and interaction (activities in small groups).

5.5.1 Physical

5.5.2 Small groups activities

5.6 Announcement detail

Information about the training day in the recruitment information.

5.7 Attention

Keeping the attention of participants active.

5.8 Cases

Examples in which course content is/could be used.

5.9 Class constellation

The way the classroom is arranged.

5.10 Discovery

Discovering the content, the meaning, the purpose, and the possible applications.

5.11 Feeling

Experiencing, feeling as opposed to cerebral, cognitive.

5.12 Known communication techniques

Communication skills, techniques, and tips that are not new.

5.13 Mind

Cerebral, cognitive.

5.14 Modelling

Mimicking, learning from examples.

5.15 Navigation and structure

Navigation and structure. Information about the day's planning (navigation) and the instructions for the activities. Often linked to the trainer. Also, pronunciation and formulation.

5.16 New communication techniques

Communication skills, techniques, and tips that have not been associated with effective communication.

5.17 New training techniques

Training techniques not experienced or even heard of before.

5.18 No expectations / open mind

Attitude of openness.

5.19 Old wine

Old wine in new bottles: common good practices and principles of communication (in a new teaching method).

5.20 Original

Creative and new.

5.21 Other participants

Referring to the attitude or behaviour of other participants.

5.22 Practice

As opposed to theoretical parts in the training day.

5.23 Role play

As an expectation for the practice part of a course.

5.24 Several training techniques

Variation and skillful teaching.

5.25 Slideshow

Referring to the use of the slides.

5.25.1 Course hand-out

Referring to the course hand-out.

5.26 Tips and tricks

Practical tips and tricks to take home.

5.27 Translating theory into practice

A relevant mixture of theory and practice.

5.28 Variation

Variation in the teaching methods throughout the training day.

6 Trainer parameters

6.1 Articulate (voice)

6.2 Assertive

6.3 Competent

6.4 Culturally different

6.5 Diplomatic

6.6 Dynamic

6.7 Enthusiast

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